

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

Adaptive measuring trajectory for scanning lidars: proof of concept

To cite this article: Yiyin Chen *et al* 2022 *J. Phys.: Conf. Ser.* **2265** 022099

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Power curve measurement of a floating offshore wind turbine with a nacelle-based lidar](#)
Umut Özinan, Dexing Liu, Raphaël Adam et al.
- [Investigation of the nacelle blockage effect for a downwind turbine](#)
Benjamin Anderson, Emmanuel Branlard, Ganesh Vijayakumar et al.
- [Lidar-based Research and Innovation at DTU Wind Energy – a Review](#)
T Mikkelsen

Adaptive measuring trajectory for scanning lidars: proof of concept

Yiyin Chen¹, Wei Yu¹, Feng Guo² and Po Wen Cheng¹

¹ Stuttgart Wind Energy at University of Stuttgart, Allmandring 5B, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany.

² Wind Energy Technology Institute, Flensburg University of Applied Sciences, Kanzleistraße 91-93, 24943 Flensburg, Germany.

E-mail: chen@ifb.uni-stuttgart.de

Abstract. Application of nacelle-mounted long-range scanning lidars is facing the challenge that the nacelle motion causes deviations in the measuring trajectories. Such lidars are very sensitive to even the slightest trajectory deviation due to its long measuring range. Motivated by this need, we propose the concept of adaptive measuring trajectory and explore its use for eliminating the effect of the rotational motion of the lidar on the target measuring trajectory. This work first aims to experimentally test the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory under ideal conditions by installing a scanning lidar on a 6DOF motion platform to model the lidar motion on the turbine nacelle. The real trajectory with and without correction is measured by a camera. The comparison confirms that the adaptive measuring trajectory could stabilize the target measuring trajectory given the lidar motion. Then, the possibility of using Kalman filter to estimate lidar motion given noisy motion measurements is investigated. The results show great potential of Kalman filter for lidar motion estimation, which could be very useful for its future application.

1. Introduction

In recent years, long-range scanning lidars have found its application in many fields in wind energy, e.g., site assessment, minute-scale power forecasting, and detection of extreme gusts and wind ramps. When referring to long-range scanning lidars, we mean Doppler wind lidars that can measure up to 12 km and have flexible user-defined measuring trajectories. Due to such a long measuring range, this type of lidars are very sensitive to even the slightest deviation from the target measuring trajectory. To give an intuitive example: a deviation of just 1° in the pitch direction leads to a deviation of about 87 m in the measuring height at 5 km distance. Considering the inhomogeneity of the atmospheric surface layer, such deviations may introduce a great deal of uncertainty into wind measurements. Moreover, the lidar measuring range may be significantly reduced when the laser hits the ground, the sea surface or clouds due to pitch deviations. Therefore, for those applications where lidars are typically mounted on the nacelle of wind turbines, the impact on lidar measuring trajectories and consequently on lidar measurements caused by the constant motion of the lidar (essentially the motion of the wind turbine nacelle) should not be ignored. And this issue becomes more critical when it comes to floating offshore wind turbines (FOWTs).

Facing this challenge, we want to propose a new concept for scanning lidars — we call it

Content from this work may be used under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 licence](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/). Any further distribution of this work must maintain attribution to the author(s) and the title of the work, journal citation and DOI.

adaptive measuring trajectory. As its name implies, the measuring trajectory is supposed to be made adaptive to cope with factors that may affect the quality of lidar measurements or to meet changing requirements that cannot be completely pre-defined. Regarding the latter use, a recent research tried to adjust the measuring trajectory every half hour to follow the prevailing wind direction [1], which can be considered as one of the initial attempts to apply an adaptive measuring trajectory.

2. Objectives

Current scanning lidars can perform flexible measuring trajectories defined by e.g. the spherical coordinates of target measuring points because its scanning head can be oriented towards any direction within the upper hemisphere with the motors inside (small negative elevation angles could also be allowed). Based on this flexibility, we aim to explore the possibility of using an adaptive measuring trajectory to compensate the effect of the rotational motion of the lidar on the target measuring trajectory. The main idea is that if it would be possible to add a control loop to the control system of the lidar scanning head to correct the deviation of the laser beam direction caused by the rotational motion of the lidar before the scanning head moves towards each target measuring point, the target measuring trajectory could remain unaffected by the lidar motion. The basic concept of the adaptive measuring trajectory is illustrated in Fig. 1. This concept can also be understood as a sort of motion compensation on the measuring trajectory level. Although the focus of range gates of the lidar may also move due to the translational motion of the nacelle, the correction of range gates is not considered in this research because the positioning of range gates is defined by time windows for segmenting backscattered laser signals in lidar data post-processing, which is a different mechanism.

Figure 1. Basic concept of the adaptive measuring trajectory for scanning lidars.

However, because no scanning lidars can support this adaptive measuring trajectory currently, we mainly focus on proof of concept using experimental and numerical approaches. The first part of this work is to experimentally test the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory under ideal conditions. Because the key to this concept is to accurately estimate the lidar motion or rather the nacelle motion of wind turbines, in the second part, we investigate the potential of an optimal estimator — Kalman filter using simulations.

3. Experimental study: testing the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory

3.1. Concept and experimental setup

In the first part of this research, the ideal performance of adaptive measuring trajectory is tested in a lab environment. The concept of the experiment is shown in Fig. 2. A scanning lidar is installed on a 6DOF motion platform¹ to model the motion during its operation on the nacelle of the LIFES50+² public FOWT design OO-Star, configuration details of which can be found in [2]. The nacelle motion is simulated by a high fidelity model to capture as many physical effects and degrees of freedom as possible. Here OpenFAST³ is chosen, which is already widely used as an

¹ <https://motionsystems.eu/product/motion-platforms/ps-6tm-150/>, last access: 24.01.2022

² <https://lifes50plus.eu/>, last access: 21.01.2022

³ <https://github.com/OpenFAST/openfast>, last access: on 21.01.2022

engineering model for FOWTs. The wind and wave conditions considered in this research are based on the site specific definition of the project LIFES50+, including below rated, rated, and above rated operation of the FOWT. The turbulent wind fields were generated with the Mann turbulence generator⁴ (MTG). The nacelle motion is fed into the motion platform to physically generate the motion so that the lidar inclinometer can measure the lidar motion. Because the input motion signals do not contain any noises, the experiment condition is considered ideal. The corrected trajectory is calculated according to the lidar motion measured by the inclinometer to compensate its effects, i.e.,

$$\text{corrected trajectory} = \text{target trajectory} - \text{lidar motion}. \quad (1)$$

For simplicity, the target measuring trajectory is set to the starring mode pointing straight ahead. Because the laser of the lidar is invisible, a visible laser source is installed on the scanning head so that the trajectory can be measured by a camera. The method of measuring lidar trajectory with a camera is introduced in Sect. 3.2. Limited by the lab space, we consider only the pitch motion and the corresponding elevation angle correction of the lidar trajectory in the experiment. The mean value of the pitch motion is removed to prevent the lidar from tilting to much on the motion platform. The experimental setup is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 2. Testing the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory in a lab environment.

Because the lidar does not support real-time updating of the measuring trajectory, the experiment needs to be broken down into two phases: in the first phase, the target trajectory is input into the lidar and the goal is to measure the lidar motion and validate the trajectory measurement of the camera; in the second phase, the corrected trajectory is input into the lidar given the same lidar motion as in the first phase so that the performance of the corrected trajectory can be evaluated by comparing the trajectory measurements of both phases.

3.2. Measuring lidar trajectory with a camera

This section introduces the approach of measuring lidar trajectory with a camera. To obtain as high spatial resolution as possible, all experimental videos were taken with a 4K resolution (3840 × 2160 pixels) at 24 frames per second. The video processing is done using the MATLAB image processing toolbox and consists of the following steps:

- Camera calibration [3]: After setting up the camera position, the camera needs to be calibrated to estimate the parameters of the lens and the image sensor, which are necessary to undistort images and map the world coordinates to the image coordinates in next steps. For this purpose, a calibration pattern, in this case, a 7 × 10 asymmetric checkerboard with

⁴ <https://www.hawc2.dk/download/pre-processing-tools>, last access: 24.01.2022

Figure 3. Experimental setup. (a) Schematic diagram. (b)-(d) Photos.

a square size of 25 mm is affixed to the door on which the visible laser is projected and to be measured. A short video of the calibration pattern is taken from different angles as the input of the calibration algorithm. Please note that camera calibration must be done every time the camera is repositioned.

- Image undistortion: After importing the experimental videos as images, the images need to be undistorted to eliminate the distortion caused by the lens so that the trajectory can be measured precisely.
- Detecting moving laser spots in videos: To make the detection of laser spots easier, the videos were deliberately recorded in the dark. The RGB images are first converted to greyscale images and then further converted to black and white images by taking a greyscale threshold to detect the brightest part of the laser spot. This part is approximately a circle, and thus its center is detected as the position of the laser spot.
- Mapping the world coordinates to the image coordinates: With this step, the pixel coordinates of the detected laser spot centers can be converted to world coordinates.

3.3. Experimental results

In the first phase of the experiment, the target trajectory is input into the lidar. The lidar pitch motion measured by the inclinometer is used to validate the trajectory measurement of the camera and to calculate the corrected trajectory using Eq. (1). The raw measurement of the camera is the vertical motion of the laser spot, which can be converted to the pitch angle using the distance from the laser source to the door as illustrated in Fig. 3a. Figure 4 shows a comparison among the motion system input and output of the pitch motion and the pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer and the camera from the first phase of the experiment. The motion system input is the pitch motion signal fed into the motion system. The motion system output is the pitch motion signal calculated with the real-time arm angles of the motion system, which can be understood as the pitch motion that really happens. As shown in Fig. 4a, the pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer and the motion system output match each other well, while both slightly deviates from the motion system input. Therefore, we consider the measurement of the lidar inclinometer to be accurate in lab conditions and use it as the reference of the real pitch motion. The reasons for the real pitch motion produced by the motion system having a

slight deviation from the input signal might be the acceleration limitation of the motion system or additional forces among arms caused by the mounting frame of the lidar, etc. The good match between the pitch motion measured by the camera and the lidar inclinometer displayed in Fig. 4b proves that the camera measurement is sufficiently accurate for this research.

Figure 4. Validation of the camera measurement of the lidar trajectory. The example shown is for the rated condition of 12 m s^{-1} . The mean value of the pitch motion has been removed. (a) Timeseries data of the input and output pitch motion of the motion system, the lidar measured and camera measured pitch motion. (b) Comparison of the lidar measured and camera measured pitch motion. The best-fit curve is $y = 1.019x + 0.022$ with $R^2 = 0.9982$.

In the second phase, the corrected trajectory shown in Fig. 5a is input into the lidar given the same pitch motion as in the first phase. Figure 5b compares the real lidar trajectories (the position of the laser spot on the door) with and without trajectory corrections measured with the camera. Since the sample time of the lidar scanning head performing the measuring trajectory is not completely regular, the corrected trajectory sometimes cannot exactly match the pitch motion, which might lead to poor correction during drastic elevation angle changes. However, this is only a limitation of this experiment and could hopefully be avoided when the correction is done in real-time by a control system of the lidar itself. Nevertheless, the results confirm that the concept of adaptive measuring trajectory would bring significant improvements in stabilizing the target measuring trajectory, especially when we look at the second y axis in Fig. 5b, which intuitively shows the height deviation of the measuring point at 5 km distance caused by the lidar pitch motion as an example. Therefore, we hope this concept could be made possible in the future.

4. Numerical study: investigating Kalman filter for lidar motion estimation

4.1. Concept and numerical framework

In the first part of the research, the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory has been experimentally tested with known lidar motion, which is an ideal condition. However, in practice, measurements of lidar motion are never perfect and usually contain noises. This issue might become the barrier of the application of the adaptive measuring trajectory because it requires accurate estimation of the lidar motion. Motivated by this, in the second part, we explore the potential of Kalman filter (KF) for optimal estimation of the lidar motion using Simulink. Because lidar motion is typically measured with the lidar inclinometer if no additional measuring device is deployed, here we study the effect of applying a KF to the lidar inclinometer as an example.

KF can provide the optimal state estimates by combining the predicted state estimates produced by a system dynamics model and noisy measurements [4]. To test a KF with

Figure 5. Evaluation of adaptive measuring trajectory. The mean wind speed is 12 m s^{-1} and the mean value of the pitch motion has been removed. (a) The pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer, the target trajectory, and the corrected trajectory. (b) The video measurements of the trajectories with and without the trajectory correction. The second y axis shows the height deviation of the measuring point at 5 km distance caused by the lidar pitch motion as an example.

simulations, we need a high fidelity model of a FOWT representing the real dynamic system to produce reference nacelle motion, a linear system dynamics model of the FOWT to be input into the KF, and an approach to model the noisy measurements taken by the lidar inclinometer during the operation of the lidar on the nacelle. For the high fidelity FOWT model, we use the same simulations from OpenFAST as in the experimental study. For the linear FOWT model, we apply the simplified low order floating wind turbine (SLOW) model developed by [5], which is briefly introduced in Sect. 4.2. Because the SLOW model requires the rotor effective wind speed (REWS) as an input, the concept presented in Fig. 2 for the experimental study is modified and extended to include a lidar simulator and all necessary algorithms for estimating REWS from lidar preview measurements, shown in Fig. 6. The methodology of lidar simulation and REWS estimation is explained in Sect. 4.3. To model more realistic measurement noises of the lidar motion measured by the lidar inclinometer, we did a basic noise analysis with some measurements from the project VAMOS⁵, which is given in Sect. 4.4. Section 4.5 discusses the performance of KF.

4.2. Linearized SLOW model

The SLOW model is intended to represent the system dynamics of FOWTs with only physical effects relevant to the purpose of conceptual design and control design [5]. The model applications were presented in [6–10]. The SLOW model consists of a structural model and sub-models for external aerodynamics, hydrodynamics, and mooring loads. The structural model is based on a flexible multi-body system (MBS) formulation with a rigid platform and a flexible

⁵ <https://www.ifb.uni-stuttgart.de/forschung/windenergie/forschungsprojekte/vamos/>, last access: 24.01.2022

Figure 6. Applying Kalman filter to estimate the nacelle motion of a FOWT using simulations.

tower. The system state vector is written as

$$\mathbf{x} = [x_p, z_p, \beta_p, x_t, \theta, \varphi, \dot{x}_p, \dot{z}_p, \dot{\beta}_p, \dot{x}_t, \dot{\theta}, \dot{\omega}]^T, \quad (2)$$

with x_p, z_p, β_p the surge, heave, and pitch motions of the platform, x_t the fore-aft tower top deformation, θ the blade pitch angle, and φ and ω the azimuth and rotational speed of the rotor. For the external forces, the aerodynamics are represented through a rigid actuator disc. A look-up table based on the aerodynamic torque and thrust coefficients for each tip speed ratio and blade pitch angle is created for the quasi-static aerodynamic forces and their derivatives at each operation points. The three catenary mooring lines are represented by a quasi-static model, which results in a 6×6 stiffness matrix in the linearized formulation, for each operating point. The frequency-dependent wave excitation force vectors are calculated by the hydrodynamic panel code Ansys-AQWA, and the additional viscous drag damping is captured by the linearized Morison equation according to [11].

4.3. Lidar simulation and estimation of rotor effective wind speed from lidar measurements

The simulation of line-of-sight (LOS) measurements of a pulsed lidar is done with the widely used discrete approximation method [12, 13] explained as follows. At each time step t , the LOS measurement $v_{\text{los}}(r_0, t)$ at the focus position r_0 of a range gate is approximated by the weighted average of the LOS point measurements at N_{rw} discrete positions considered for modeling the lidar probe volume effect using the discrete lidar weighting function $\varphi(r_k)$. The LOS point measurement at each discrete position r_k is calculated by projecting the wind velocity vector $\mathbf{v}_k = [u_k, v_k, w_k]^T$ into the direction of the lidar measuring beam with its normal vector $\mathbf{n} = [x_n, y_n, z_n]^T$. In addition, we consider the wind evolution between the upstream wind field for the lidar simulations and the wind field at the rotor position for the FAST simulations and the impact of nacelle motion (including the motion of the floating platform) on the lidar simulations as shown in Fig. 6. The 4D wind field generation tool evoTurb [13, 14] is applied in combination with the MTG to simulate 4D turbulent wind fields considering a medium wind evolution scenario [15]. The nacelle motion velocity vector $\mathbf{v}_{\text{nac}} = [u_{\text{nac}}, v_{\text{nac}}, w_{\text{nac}}]^T$ obtained from the FAST simulations is projected into the LOS direction to account for the component contributed by the nacelle motion. The lidar simulation method can be summarized by the

formula below:

$$v_{\text{los}}(r_0, t) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_{\text{rw}}} \varphi(r_k) \cdot \mathbf{v}_k(r_k, t) \cdot \mathbf{n}(r_k, t) + \mathbf{v}_{\text{nac}}(t) \cdot \mathbf{n}(r_k, t). \quad (3)$$

To estimate REWS from lidar measurements for the current time step t , we use the LOS measurement of the previous time step $t - t_s$, with t_s the time shift of wind traveling from the position of the LOS measurement to the rotor. A motion compensation algorithm is applied to remove the contribution from the nacelle motion to the LOS wind speed (the opposite of the above steps). The wind field reconstruction for the u component is done by assuming perfect turbine alignment. The REWS is approximated by the averaged u component over the part of the rotor plane covered by the lidar scan pattern. In this case, the most commonly used scan pattern for a long range lidar — plan position indicator (PPI) is assumed, which measures a horizontal area with an open angle of 60° . The equation for estimating REWS from lidar measurements is [13, 16, 17]

$$v_{0L} = \frac{1}{x_{n,j}} \frac{1}{N_R} \sum_{j=1}^{N_R} v_{\text{los},j}, \quad (4)$$

with $v_{\text{los},j}$ the j th LOS measurement, $x_{n,j}$ the first element of the normal vector of the j th measuring position, and N_R the total number of lidar measuring positions within the rotor plane.

4.4. Noise analysis of the lidar pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer

To generate more realistic noises to model the pitch motion measured by a lidar inclinometer, we tried to understand the characteristics of its measurement noises by performing a basic analysis of some measured data taken in the measurement campaign carried out in the SEM-REV test site⁶ in France within the project VAMOS. In this measurement campaign, a lidar system was installed on the nacelle of a FOWT to measure the turbine inflow conditions. In addition, an inertial measurement unit (IMU) was also installed on the turbine nacelle to measure the nacelle motion. Because the IMU measurements provided by the project partner BW-Ideol⁷ have been post-processed and thus are considered as better motion estimates, the pitch motion measured by the IMU is regarded as the reference, i.e., the "real" pitch, in the noise analysis.

First of all, we compared the pitch motion measured with the IMU and the lidar inclinometer in a scatter plot (see Fig. 7a) and found a clear linear relationship between them, with a linear coefficient of 2.7743. Then, we scaled down the pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer by the linear coefficient and calculated the deviation between it and the real pitch as follows:

$$\text{deviation} = \frac{\text{lidar measured pitch}}{\text{linear coefficient}} - \text{real pitch}. \quad (5)$$

Interestingly, we found that the deviation conforms a hyperbolic secant distribution [18] with the following parameters (see Fig. 7b):

$$f(x : \mu, \sigma) = \frac{1}{2\sigma} \text{sech} \left[\frac{\pi}{2} \left(\frac{x - \mu}{\sigma} \right) \right] \quad \text{with} \quad \mu = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \sigma = 0.4405. \quad (6)$$

It must be emphasized that because the noise analysis is not the focus of this research, it was done on a very simple level with measurements of a short period. If long-term data is involved, the

⁶ <https://sem-rev.ec-nantes.fr/>, last access: 24.03.2022

⁷ <https://www.bw-ideol.com/en>, last access: 03.04.2022

best-fit for the deviation might not necessarily be the hyperbolic secant distribution. However, for simplicity, we decided to generate random signals based on the above probability density function (PDF) for simulating the measurement noises of the pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer in this work.

Figure 7. (a) Comparison of the real lidar pitch motion and the pitch motion measured by the lidar inclinometer. For confidentiality reasons, the axis values are not allowed to be displayed. (b) Histogram and the fitted PDF of the deviation between the real lidar pitch motion and the scaled lidar measured pitch motion.

4.5. Evaluation of the performance of Kalman filter

KF is based on the following linear continuous-time state-space model:

$$\dot{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{u}_K + \mathbf{w}_K, \quad (7a)$$

$$\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{u}_K + \mathbf{v}_K, \quad (7b)$$

with \mathbf{A} , \mathbf{B} , \mathbf{C} , and \mathbf{D} the state-space matrices. \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} are obtained from the SLOW model. \mathbf{C} is used to define which system state has available measurements. \mathbf{D} is $\mathbf{0}$ in this case. The known input vector \mathbf{u}_K consists of the REWS, the three wave forces in the surge, heave, and pitch directions, and the two control signals, i.e., the generator torque and the blade pitch angle. For the measurement vector \mathbf{y} , only the measurement of the pitch motion β_p is assumed to be available. Because the rotor azimuth φ is an unobservable state in the above state-space model, φ must be removed from the system state vector \mathbf{x} introduced in Eq. (2) and the state-space matrices need to be adjusted accordingly. \mathbf{w}_K and \mathbf{v}_K are the white process noise vector and the white measurement noise vector, respectively. The process noise covariance \mathbf{Q} , the measurement noise covariance \mathbf{R} , and the noise cross covariance \mathbf{N} are defined as

$$\mathbf{Q} = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{w}_K \mathbf{w}_K^\top), \quad \mathbf{R} = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{v}_K \mathbf{v}_K^\top), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{N} = \mathbb{E}(\mathbf{w}_K \mathbf{v}_K^\top), \quad (8)$$

where \mathbb{E} denotes the mathematical expectation. \mathbf{Q} and \mathbf{R} are set 10^{-5} and 10^{-4} , respectively. \mathbf{N} is set 0, assuming the process and measurement noises are uncorrelated.

We evaluate the performance of the KF considering the influences of the known input REWS and different operation conditions of the FOWT. To discuss the effects of the REWS, Fig. 8 shows a comparison of the pitch motion estimated by the KF given three different REWS inputs: REWS at the rotor plane ("real" REWS), REWS at the lidar preview measurement

plane, and REWS estimated by the lidar measurements. The main difference between the first two is the effect of wind evolution. The result shows that although the REWS estimated by the lidar measurements is more fluctuating than the other two, the corresponding pitch motion estimated by the KF is as good as that of the other two. This could conclude that the KF is not very sensitive to slight fluctuations of the known inputs. To compare the performance of the KF at below rated (8 m s^{-1}), rated (12 m s^{-1}), and above rated (16 m s^{-1}) conditions, the respective simulation results are illustrated in Fig. 9. It can be concluded that the KF performs very well in all three cases and thus shows great potential as an optimal estimator for system states of FOWTs.

Figure 8. (a) Three different REWS inputs: v_0 — REWS at the rotor plane, $v_{0,pre}$ — REWS at the lidar preview measurement plane, and $v_{0,L}$ — REWS estimated with the lidar measurements. The mean wind speed is 12 m s^{-1} . (b) Comparison of the pitch motion estimated with the Kalman filter given the three REWS inputs.

5. Conclusions and outlooks

Application of nacelle-mounted long-range scanning lidars is facing the challenge that the lidar motion caused by the nacelle motion leads to deviations in the measuring trajectories. Due to the long measuring range of such lidars, even tiny deviations may introduce plenty of uncertainty into lidar measurements. Motivated by this need, we propose the concept of adaptive measuring trajectory and explore its use for eliminating the effect of the rotational motion of the lidar on the target measuring trajectory. The main idea is to add a control loop to the control system of the lidar scanning head to correct the deviation of the laser beam direction caused by the rotational motion of the lidar before the scanning head moves towards each target measuring point. If this concept could be made possible, the target measuring trajectory could remain unaffected by the lidar motion. However, such concept is currently not supported by any scanning lidars. Therefore, this research mainly focuses on proof of concept using experimental and numerical studies.

This work consists of two parts. The objective of the first part is to test the performance of adaptive measuring trajectory under ideal conditions using a lab experiment. For this purpose, a scanning lidar is installed on a 6DOF motion platform which can generate physical motion

Figure 9. Kalman filter estimation of the pitch motion of a FOWT at different operation conditions. (a) Below rated: 8 m s^{-1} . (b) Rated: 12 m s^{-1} . (c) Above rated: 16 m s^{-1} .

according to nacelle motion created by FAST simulations to model the lidar motion on the turbine nacelle. The experiment has two phases: in the first phase, the target trajectory is input into the lidar. The lidar motion is measured by the lidar inclinometer and the real trajectory of the target trajectory is measured by a camera. In the second phase, the trajectory adjusted according to the measured lidar motion is input into the lidar given the same lidar motion as in the first phase. The real trajectory of the corrected trajectory is also measured by the camera. The comparison of the real trajectories measured by the camera of both phases shows that the adaptive measuring trajectory would bring significant improvements in stabilizing the target measuring trajectory.

Because the motion measured by the lidar inclinometer could be very noisy in practice, but accurate estimation of the lidar motion is a necessary prerequisite for the application of adaptive measuring trajectory, the second part aims to explore the potential of Kalman filter for estimating lidar motion given very noisy measurements. A linearized simplified low order floating wind turbine model (SLOW) is input into the Kalman filter to assist the estimation. The results show that Kalman filter performs very well at below rated, rated, and above rated operation of a FOWT and could be very useful for the application of adaptive measuring trajectory.

Although this work is a very preliminary study on adaptive measuring trajectory, focusing on

proof of concept, the results show great potential of this concept. In the future, more research need to be done in this direction to investigate to what extent the adaptive measuring trajectory could improve the measurement quality of long-range scanning lidars considering more practical conditions.

Acknowledgments

This research received financial support from the project ParkCast (grant no. 0324330A) funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK) and the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Horizon 2020) under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. 858358 (LIKE – Lidar Knowledge Europe). The motion platform was funded by the project CROWN, which received funding from the Eurostars-2 joint programme with co-funding from the Horizon 2020. The IMU data was provided by BW-Ideol within the project VAMOS (grant no. 03EE2004A) funded by BMWK. The installation of the nacelle-based lidar in VAMOS was supported by the Horizon 2020 under grant agreement no. 731084 (MaRINET2) at the SEM-REV test infrastructure. In addition, the authors would like to show their gratitude to Philipp Berlinger, Sebastian Putzke, and Fabian Schurig for their great support for the experiment, to Wei Fu and Mohammad Salari Khaniki for their suggestions on Kalman filter, and to David Schlipf for his suggestions on lidar simulations.

References

- [1] Wildmann N, Vasiljevic N and Gerz T 2018 *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques* **11** 3801–3814 ISSN 1867-8548
- [2] Yu W, Müller K and Lemmer F 2018 Public Definition of the Two LIFES50+ 10MW Floater Concepts Tech. rep.
- [3] Zhang Z 2000 *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence* **22** 1330–1334
- [4] Zarchan P and Musoff H 2000 *Fundamentals of Kalman filtering: A practical approach / Paul Zarchan and Howard Musoff (Progress in astronautics and aeronautics vol v.190)* (Reston, Va. and Great Britain: American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics) ISBN 1563474557
- [5] Lemmer F, Yu W, Luhmann B, Schlipf D and Cheng P W 2020 *Multibody System Dynamics* **49** 203–236 ISSN 1384-5640
- [6] Lemmer F, Schlipf D and Cheng P W 2016 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **573** 092006 URL <http://stacks.iop.org/1742-6596/753/i=9/a=092006>
- [7] Lemmer F, Müller K, Yu W, Schlipf D and Cheng P W 2017 *ASME 2017 36th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering* p V010T09A080 ISBN 978-0-7918-5778-6 URL <http://proceedings.asmedigitalcollection.asme.org/proceeding.aspx?doi=10.1115/OMAE2017-62038>
- [8] Yu W, Lemmer F, Schlipf D, Cheng P W, Visser B, Links H, Gupta N, Dankemann S, Couñago B and Serna J 2018 *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* vol 1104 p 012033 ISSN 1742-6588
- [9] Lemmer F, Yu W, Cheng P W, Pegalajar-jurado A, Borg M, Mikkelsen R F and Bredmose H 2018 *Proceedings of ASME 2018 37th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering* (Madrid, Spain)
- [10] Lemmer F, Yu W and Cheng P W 2018 *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering* **6** ISSN 2077-1312 URL <http://www.mdpi.com/2077-1312/6/4/118>
- [11] Borgman L E 1965 *Proceedings of the Santa Barbara Coastal Engineering Conference* (Santa Barbara, USA) pp 147–182
- [12] Mann J, Cariou J P, Courtney M S, Parmentier R, Mikkelsen T, Wagner R, Lindelow P, Sjöholm M and Enevoldsen K 2009 *Meteorologische Zeitschrift* **18** 135
- [13] Chen Y, Guo F, Schlipf D and Cheng P W 2022 *Wind Energy Science* **7** 539–558 ISSN 2366-7451
- [14] Chen Y and Guo F 2021 evoTurb URL <https://github.com/SWE-UniStuttgart/evoTurb>
- [15] Chen Y, Schlipf D and Cheng P W 2021 *Wind Energy Science* **6** 61–91 ISSN 2366-7451
- [16] Schlipf D 2015 *Lidar-Assisted Control Concepts for Wind Turbines* Dissertation University of Stuttgart
- [17] Held D P and Mann J 2019 *Wind Energy Science* **4** 421–438 URL <https://wes.copernicus.org/articles/4/421/2019/>
- [18] Johnson N L, Kotz S and Balakrishnan N 1995- *Continuous univariate distributions* 2nd ed Wiley series in probability and mathematical statistics. Applied probability and statistics (New York and Chichester: Wiley) ISBN 978-0-471-58494-0